

A cuckoo search algorithm to improve a routing problem adapted to last mile e-commerce logistics

Alejandro Escudero-Santana^{1*}, Luis Onieva¹,
Juan Carlos Cortés Muñoz¹, María-Luisa Muñoz-Díaz¹

^{1*}Departamento de Organización Industrial y Gestión de Empresas II,
Universidad de Sevilla, Avenida de los Descubrimientos s/n, Sevilla,
41092, Andalucía, España.

*Corresponding author(s). E-mail(s): alejandroescudero@us.es;

Abstract

The rapid growth of e-commerce as an alternative to traditional face-to-face commerce has highlighted the logistical challenges of efficiently delivering goods to end consumers. A major problem is that recipients are often not available at the designated delivery locations during the delivery process, leading to reduced efficiency in last-mile logistics. This research works on a novel last-mile logistics framework where customers can provide multiple delivery points with different time windows. This logistical challenge represents a new and more complex variant of the vehicle routing problem with time windows. To address this problem, we present a metaheuristic approach using the cuckoo search algorithm. The results demonstrate that cuckoo search algorithm improves the costs on previous results achieved by other methodologies, allowing for greater efficiency in last-mile logistics planning.

Keywords: e-commerce, last mile logistics, vrp, metaheuristics, cuckoo search

1 Introduction

The impact of Business to Consumers (B2C) deliveries resulting from e-commerce transactions lacks clarity in terms of efficiency and sustainability. It leads to a notable surge in truck fleets and mileage but simultaneously contributes to reducing the need for numerous customer shopping trips within the network (Cullinane, 2009; Rotem-Mindali and Weltevreden, 2013). From the perspective of logistics operators, the

efficacy of freight vehicle trips can be significantly improved by adopting delivery at pick-up points. Despite this, home deliveries persist as the prevailing logistic strategy for online purchases (Ghezzi et al, 2012; Buldeo Rai et al, 2020).

The execution of home deliveries introduces a high level of complexity into the management of last-mile fleets, especially considering that delivery performance is a crucial factor influencing e-commerce customer satisfaction (Alam and Yasin, 2010; van Duin et al, 2016). Punctuality in deliveries consistently emerges as a key determinant of logistics performance impacting customer satisfaction in e-commerce (Ramanathan, 2010; Ghezzi et al, 2012). Delays often lead to redeliveries and a decline in perceived service quality. Moreover, delivery companies are now exploring the option of allowing customers to choose preferred delivery slots to enhance satisfaction (Xing et al, 2010). Goebel et al (2012) have demonstrated the willingness of certain socio-economic segments to pay for this time-based delivery service, emphasizing that a company offering this service reduces consumer effort and gains a competitive advantage.

Regarding fleet optimisation, managing time-based deliveries can be accomplished with a Vehicle Routing Problem with Time Windows (VRPTW) problem, where customers are assigned to time windows based on their preferred slots. Providing customers with this option increases pressure on the carrier's side, potentially leading to higher peak loads and subsequent costs, especially if most orders are scheduled for evening delivery. In contrast, our proposal aims to offer customers the flexibility to suggest different time slots associated with various locations, with the assurance that the order will be delivered at one of them. For instance, a customer could choose to receive the delivery at home early in the morning, at work during the day, or at their parents' house in the evening. This offers the carrier greater flexibility to adjust operations while maintaining the perception of delivery service quality.

This novel approach, incorporating both time and location factors, requires the development of a new methodology, as the traditional VRPTW model becomes ineffective. The existing literature, including comprehensive surveys of VRP applications and variants (Anbuudayasankar et al, 2014; Lin et al, 2014; Caceres-Cruz et al, 2014), seldom addresses the consideration of different locations for the same customer. Only a limited number of studies have explored topics aligned with those discussed in this article (Moccia et al, 2012; Tilk et al, 2021; Escudero-Santana et al, 2022). Due to the problem's complexity, this article proposes a new methodology to address such issues.

In order to elaborate a fleet optimisation under time and location restrictions, we present the mathematical model for the problem in the following section. Given its NP-hard nature, Section 3 is dedicated to describing the methodology, which is then applied to various simulation scenarios in Section 4. Finally, Section 5 analyzes the results obtained and draws conclusions.

2 Problem formulation

In this paper we propose the resolution of a problem of goods distribution routes focusing on the last mile distribution in the context of e-commerce. It is a VRPTW type problem where each customer identifies a series of locations, nodes, where the delivery could be served. Each of these locations is identified with a time window.

Several vehicles are available to make deliveries to these customers. These vehicles must depart from a depot and return to it after finishing their route. Regarding the fleet, a homogeneous fleet is considered, where all vehicles have the same characteristics and the same capacity, without this being limited by the nature of the goods (the products are considered to be small in size). Therefore, a single vehicle could serve all customers if the time restrictions allow it. It is assumed that the number of vehicles is enough to serve all customers.

A customer is considered served when delivery is made to any of the locations previously established by the customer. The fact that each customer has three (or more) possible delivery locations is due to the fact that customers can change their location over time. For example, a customer could be at home early in the morning and after a certain time they might go to work and change their location. Once a customer has been served at one of their possible locations, the other locations are no longer active, since the customer has already been served and it is only necessary to visit each of them once. The depot from which the vehicles depart also has a time window associated with it.

In the Fig. 1 we can see an example of what has been explained previously. There is a problem with 3 customers, each with 2 or 3 locations. Each customer is represented by a circle of a different colour (blue, green, red). The depot is represented as a black squared. A possible solution can also be seen, where customer green is visited at their first location (in this case is their home), then customer red is served, also at their third location, and customer two is visited at their second location (their workplace), finally returning to the depot.

Fig. 1: Problem example with three customers and solutions

This problem has been modelled as a graph $G(N, A)$ where the set of nodes N contains all of the different customer locations plus the depot, and A is the set of undirected arcs joining all of the nodes in N pairwise (Escudero-Santana et al, 2022). The following nomenclature is used:

- I : set of all customers.
- K : set of all identical vehicles.
- V_i : set of possible locations of the customer $i \in I$.
- i, j or r : a specific customer.
- k : a specific vehicle.
- v_i, v_j or v_r : a specific locations of the customer i, j , or r .
- e_{v_i} : earliest arrival time at a location v_i of customer i .
- l_{v_i} : latest arrival time at a location v_i of customer i .
- $d_{v_i v_j}$: distance between v_i and v_j .
- M : a sufficiently large constant.

The variables used in the formulation are:

- $x_{v_i v_j}^k$: takes a value of 1 if vehicle k has served to customer i at its location v_i and travel to serve customer j at its location v_j , and 0 otherwise.
- t_j : arrival time at customer j

The problem is mathematically formulated as a mixed-integer programming (MIP) as follows:

$$\text{minimize } \sum_{k \in K} \sum_{v_i \in V_i} \sum_{v_j \in V_j} d_{v_i v_j} \cdot x_{v_i v_j}^k \quad (1)$$

subject to:

$$\sum_{k \in K} \sum_{i \in I} \sum_{v_i \in V_i} \sum_{v_j \in V_j} x_{v_i v_j}^k = 1 \quad \forall j \in I \quad (2)$$

$$\sum_{k \in K} \sum_{i \in I} \sum_{v_i \in V_i} \sum_{v_j \in V_j} x_{v_i v_j}^k = 1 \quad \forall i \in I \quad (3)$$

$$\sum_{i \in I} \sum_{v_i \in V_i} x_{v_i v_j}^k = \sum_{r \in I} \sum_{v_r \in V_r} x_{v_i v_r}^k \quad \forall i \in I, \forall v_j \in V_j, \forall k \in K \quad (4)$$

$$t_i + d_{v_i v_j} \sum_{k \in K} x_{v_i v_j}^k \leq t_j + A \left(1 - \sum_{k \in K} x_{v_i v_j}^k \right) \quad \forall i, j \in I, \forall v_i \in V_i, \forall v_j \in V_j \quad (5)$$

$$e_{v_i} - A \left(1 - \sum_{k \in K} \sum_{i \in I} \sum_{v_i \in V_i} x_{v_i v_j}^k \right) \leq t_j \quad \forall j \in I, \forall v_j \in V_j \quad (6)$$

$$t_j \leq l_{v_j} - A \left(1 - \sum_{k \in K} \sum_{i \in I} \sum_{v_i \in V_i} x_{v_i v_j}^k \right) \quad \forall j \in I, \forall v_j \in V_j \quad (7)$$

$$\sum_{j \in I} \sum_{v_j \in V_j} x_{0 v_j}^k = 1 \quad \forall k \in K \quad (8)$$

$$\sum_{i \in I} \sum_{v_i \in V_I} x_{v_j 0}^k = 1 \quad \forall k \in K \quad (9)$$

$$x_{v_i v_j}^k \in 0, 1 \quad (10)$$

$$t_j \geq 0 \quad (11)$$

The objective function 1 is to minimise the total length of the routes. The constraints presented in Eqs. 2 and 3 are used to ensure that vehicles serve all customer orders. Meanwhile, Eq. 4 dictate that each vehicle must arrive at and depart from each node within the same specified location. Furthermore, Eq. 5 specify that the arrival time at customer j , visited after customer i , cannot exceed the arrival time at customer i . Eqs. 6 and 7 define the permissible range of arrival times for each customer location, taking into account their specific time windows. In addition, Eqs. 8 and 9 require that all vehicles in the fleet start and end their routes at the depot. This requirement exists despite the possibility of using a direct loop that starts and ends at the depot, thus incurring zero cost for unused vehicles.

3 Methodology

The Cuckoo Search (CS) algorithm (Yang and Deb, 2010; Yang and He, 2016) is inspired by the aggressive breeding strategy of some cuckoo species, combined with the Lévy Flight behaviour present in some bird species (Gandomi et al, 2013). This methodology was first presented by Yang and Deb (2010). A survey of its applications can be found in Ali et al (2021) and Shehab et al (2017).

3.1 Bio-inspired foundations

Cuckoo are known not only for the unusual sound they make, but also for their peculiar and aggressive reproductive strategy. Some of their species, such as the Ani or the Guira, lay their eggs in the nests of other birds (host birds), even eliminating the eggs of the other species to increase the probability that their eggs will hatch. To ensure successful incubation, cuckoos often lay their eggs in the nests of birds whose eggs are similar in colour and texture. At the same time, host birds develop the ability to identify "intruder" eggs laid by cuckoos. If the host bird discovers that the eggs are not its own, it either discards the intruding eggs or simply abandons the nest and builds another, changing its location. It is expected that this breeding behaviour may have evolutionary advantages, saving time and effort in rearing and, therefore, allowing cuckoos to concentrate on maximizing egg laying in multiple host nests, thereby increasing their reproductive capacity.

3.2 The Cuckoo Search

CS is based on three ideal rules:

- Each cuckoo lays one egg at a time in a randomly chosen nest.
- Eggs laid in better quality nests are passed on to subsequent generations.

- The number of host nests is fixed and the host bird can discover an egg laid in a nest with a probability of $p_a \in [0, 1]$.

Following these idealised rules, it is necessary to establish some relationships between the source of inspiration and the search space. Several interpretations are presented below:

- Each egg in a nest represents one solution and each nest will contain only one egg. Multiple eggs in a nest might be possible, but for simplicity of application only one is contemplated.
- Each cuckoo bird will lay only one egg at a time and will choose the nest randomly. Therefore, each individual in the cuckoo population has the right to randomly generate a single solution.
- The best nests, with the best solutions, will advance to the next generation.
- New solutions should be generated through Lévy Flight, around the best solutions.
- The number of host nests is fixed, and an egg laid in a nest can be discovered by the host bird with a probability of $p_a \in [0, 1]$. In this situation, the host bird chooses between abandoning the nest or removing the egg. For simplicity, this assumption can be approximated by replacing a fraction p_a of the nests by other new nests (with random solutions in new locations). For maximization problems, the quality or fitness of the nests is proportional to the objective function of the problem.

Following these principles, we present the algorithm used in this work. The methodology consists of several phases. The first phase (see algorithm 1) involves the population initialization and the parameterization of the method. The second phase (see algorithm 2) involves the improvement of the initial population using the CS algorithm.

Algorithm 1 Initialization

- 1: *stop_criterion, n, pa = set_initial_parameter()*
 - 2: *nests = generate_random_initial_population(n)*
 - 3: *nests_fitness = evaluate(nests)*
 - 4: *best_nest, best_fitness = find_best(nests, nests_fitness)*
 - 5: *number_abandoned_nests = pa * n*
-

3.3 Adaptation to the problem

The adaptation of the CS to the VRPTWDO (Vehicle Routing Problem with Time Windows and Delivery Options) is based on the one performed by [Ouaarab et al \(2014\)](#) to the Travelling Agent Problem (TSP). The process of adapting the CS to the EC-VRP is based on the interpretation of the terminology explained in the previous section. The CS and its sources of inspiration can be structured and explained by the following main elements: egg and nest (since each nest have a unique egg), objective function, search space and Lévy Flight. These are explained in detail below.

Algorithm 2 Improvement

```
1: while !stopcriterion do
2:   egg, egg_fitness = select_random_egg(nests)
3:   new_egg = levy_flight(egg)
4:   new_egg_fitness = evaluate(new_egg)
5:   if new_egg_fitness < egg_fitness then
6:     egg = new_egg
7:     egg_fitness = new_egg_fitness
8:   end if
9:   abandoned_nest = abandoned(nests, number_abandoned_nests)
10:  for nest in abandoned_nest do
11:    nest.egg = levy_flight(nest.egg)
12:    nest.egg_fitness = evaluate(nest.egg)
13:  end for
14: end while
```

3.3.1 The Egg: solution representation

A solution is represented by means of a vector with $n_{location}$ elements. Where $n_{location} = (\sum_{i \in I} \sum_{v_i \in V_i} 1)$ is the total number of locations of customers.

The vector denotes the sequence in which potential customer requests are addressed. As the delivery to a customer may take place in several locations, only the first appearance is taken into account. Let us suppose that there are three customers, each with three potential locations. Then, we have $c_1 = 1, 2, 3$, $c_2 = 4, 5, 6$, and $c_3 = 7, 8, 9$, where each number is a customer execution with a location and a time window. Consequently, one possible solution is $egg1 = 1, 9, 2, 3, 5, 8, 7, 6, 4$. Since the customer has only provided one possible delivery option, the solution would be $egg1^* = 1, 9, 5$.

3.3.2 Objective functions

The objective function is represented in Eq. 1. However, this function can be adapted to different considerations of variable costs by displacement and fixed costs per vehicle.

The evaluation of the solution follows a heuristic (see 3) procedure that determines the distance and the number of vehicles needed to implement the solution.

3.3.3 The Lévy Flight and search space

The following equation (Eq. 12) produces a new solution egg_i^{t+1} , for a solution i , by a Lévy flight, where α represents the step length that follows the Lévy distribution.

$$egg_i^{t+1} = egg_i^t + \alpha \otimes Levy(s, \gamma) \quad (12)$$

Lévy flights are characterised by an intensive search around a solution, followed by occasional large jumps. According to Yang and Deb (2009), for some optimisation problems, it is more efficient to use Lévy flights to search for new and good solutions.

Algorithm 3 Evaluation

Require: egg^*

```
1:  $index = 1$ 
2:  $depot\_location = (0, 0)$ 
3:  $current\_location = depot\_location$ 
4:  $current\_time = 0$ 
5:  $total\_distance = 0$ 
6:  $number\_vehicles = 1$ 
7: while  $index \leq length(egg^*)$  do
8:    $next\_location = location(egg[index])$ 
9:    $next\_ea\_tw = early\_arrival(egg[index])$ 
10:   $next\_la\_tw = late\_arrival(egg[index])$ 
11:   $distance\_next = distance(current\_location, next\_location)$ 
12:   $next\_arrival = [distance\_next \cdot velocity] + current\_time$ 
13:  if  $next\_arrival \leq next\_la\_tw$  then
14:     $current\_time = max(next\_ea\_tw, next\_arrival)$ 
15:     $total\_distance = total\_distance + distance\_next$ 
16:     $current\_location = next\_location$ 
17:     $index = index + 1$ 
18:  else
19:     $distance\_next = distance(current\_location, depot\_location)$ 
20:     $total\_distance = total\_distance + distance\_next$ 
21:     $number\_vehicles = number\_vehicles + 1$ 
22:     $current\_location = depot\_location$ 
23:     $current\_time = 0$ 
24:  end if
25: end while
26:  $cost = number\_vehicles \cdot cost\_per\_vehicle + total\_distance \cdot cost\_per\_kilometer$ 
```

The step of a movement is the distance between two solutions. The length of this step marks which type of movement will be used. The step is based on the typology of the search space and the concept of neighbourhood. Therefore, in the present work, smaller step lengths are represented by SHIFT-1-0 and 2-OPT, while larger jumps are represented by the DOUBLE-BRIDGE movement (Ouaarab et al, 2014)

3.3.4 Algorithm parameters tuning

The CS algorithm has two parameters to set: the number of nests and the number of iterations. We tested different combinations of these parameters (See Fig. 2). The best combination, selected for the simulation, was obtained with 25 nests and 35000 iterations.

The parameter p_a was set to 0.25, which means that in each iteration 25% of the nests are abandoned. This value was established based on the analyzed literature where all algorithmic applications use this value. Additionally, different simulations

were performed by modifying the value of p_a to verify that they do not improve the results.

(a) Mean solution

(b) Execution time (min)

Fig. 2: Cuckoo Search parameters tuning (number of iterations and number of nests). (a) Mean solution, (b) execution time.

4 Results

A battery of problems has been generated to test the performance of the CS. The battery is based on the battery generated by Solomon (1987). Due to the characteristics of the VRPTWDO, explained above, the customers result from grouping the customers defined in Solomon's file 3 by 3, since each one has three realisations, which means 3 different positions and 3 different time windows. Problems with 25, 50 and 100 customers have been generated, that is, with 75, 150 and 300 different locations.

The problem solutions are shown in the Tables 1, 2 and 3. For every instance, the problem is run 10 times. The best solution found, the mean solution and the deviation are represented, as well as the execution time in minutes.

Table 1: Results of problems with 25 customer. 25 nest and 35.000 iterations

Problem	Mean	Best	Deviation	Time
r_25_1	354,57	347,26	7,23	8,29
r_25_2	314,71	298,62	10,67	7,94
r_25_3	295,71	281,05	12,35	7,51
r_25_4	254,99	232,50	12,26	7,50
r_25_5	328,60	311,95	10,39	7,85
r_25_6	296,96	265,34	15,20	7,73
r_25_7	282,58	272,68	6,35	7,62
r_25_8	253,88	228,46	15,05	7,37
r_25_9	287,37	270,11	14,24	7,65
r_25_10	274,89	240,53	22,07	7,87
r_25_11	283,39	243,78	16,77	7,49
r_25_12	267,87	228,89	19,01	7,33

Table 2: Results of problems with 50 customers. 25 nests and 35.000 iterations

Problem	Mean	Best	Deviation	Time
r_50_1	1095,13	1010,57	46,67	15,81
r_50_2	945,82	852,26	47,01	15,78
r_50_3	773,84	685,45	57,37	15,45
r_50_4	682,70	595,55	58,24	15,03
r_50_5	1001,31	921,91	56,26	16,49
r_50_6	906,24	832,85	60,41	15,05
r_50_7	762,86	678,56	44,13	15,28
r_50_8	681,56	612,87	44,91	15,65
r_50_9	889,31	813,11	51,89	16,17
r_50_10	829,18	783,44	22,84	15,08

Table 3: Results of problems with 100 customers. 25 nests and 35.000 iterations

Problem	Mean	Best	Deviation	Time
r_100_1	3328,36	3169,42	92,25	31,55
r_100_2	2773,63	2630,87	73,72	31,73
r_100_3	2305,95	2057,58	118,10	29,91
r_100_4	2119,26	1951,53	124,52	29,53
r_100_5	3123,89	2844,02	126,54	31,93
r_100_6	2725,02	2566,09	88,029	30,60
r_100_7	2317,71	2138,99	100,97	29,60
r_100_8	2091,01	1898,91	96,59	28,81
r_100_9	2930,84	2751,56	82,79	30,55
r_100_10	2646,16	2553,64	70,34	30,57

The results achieved with the CS are compared with other algorithms: Tabu Search, Simulated Annealing and Evolutionary Algorithm ([Escudero-Santana et al, 2022](#)), as is shown in Fig. 3. The comparison indicates that the algorithm performs well in terms of solution quality, consistently achieving the best mean results across all battery tests and identifying the best solution in 9 out of 10 tests. However, the CS shows poorer performance in terms of execution time. While this is not a limitation for generating an initial solution, such as planning daily deliveries, the algorithm is not suitable for real-time re-planning, where quick response is essential. This rescheduling becomes necessary when real-time factors need to be incorporated into the planning, such as fluctuating traffic conditions, live customer demand, and other dynamic changes

(a) Mean solution

(b) Best solution

(c) Execution time

Fig. 3: Comparison of results for Genetic Algorithm (GA) in blue, Tabu Search (TS) in red, Simulated Annealing (SA) in green, and Cuckoo Search (CS) in purple. (a) Mean solution, (b) best solution, (c) execution time in seconds

5 Conclusions

In e-commerce logistics, one of the key challenges is to improve the reliability of the final step of the distribution chain (last mile). It is at this final delivery point that many delivery incidents occur, resulting in the failure of the delivery of goods and causing inefficiency in the process. The most common incident is the unavailability of the user when the package is about to be delivered. Derived from the increasing logistical complexity of the last mile delivery of e-commerce, it is necessary to establish delivery strategies that help to reduce the rate of failed deliveries.

Both distribution companies and researchers have addressed this challenge and there are different proposals that attempt to alleviate this inconvenience. This paper proposes a methodology that through an increase of delivery possibilities foresees a reduction of failed deliveries.

This leads to a new routing problem, which increases the complexity of the mathematical problem to be solved by the number of possibilities provided to the consumer, so it is necessary to develop appropriate solution methodologies.

This work presents a CS method that demonstrates strong performance in generating high quality solutions to the proposed problem. While the algorithm has a longer solution time, making it less suitable for real-time replanning environments, it remains highly effective for initial planning stages where solution quality is paramount. Future improvements could focus on adapting the algorithm to dynamic environments, potentially improving its application in real-time scenarios.

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